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HYPERTHERMIA OF UNCLEAR GENESIS IN CHILDREN. A CLINICAL CASE REPORT

Abstract:

Fever of unknown origin remains one of the most difficult diagnostic problems in medicine. Since fever of unknown origin can be caused by more than 200 malignant/neoplastic, infectious, rheumatic/inflammatory and various diseases. Fever is the most common symptom in children and can be classified as fever with or without a focus. Fever without focal point can last less than 7 days and is classified as fever without localizing signs and fever of unknown origin (FUO). FUO is defined as a temperature above 38.3 °C for more than 3 weeks or the inability to establish a diagnosis after 1 week of inpatient studies. The most common causes of FUO in children are infections, connective tissue diseases and neoplasms.

Keywords: *fever, children, FUO, infections, prolonged fever.*

The most common infectious diseases in children with FUO are salmonellosis, tuberculosis, malaria, and rickettsiosis. Juvenile rheumatic arthritis is a connective tissue disease that is often associated with FUO. Malignant tumors are the third largest group responsible for FUO in children [1].

Fever is the result of immune system activation in response to infectious or non-infectious agents. In this case, a disorder involving the immune mechanism is suspected, which may include autoimmune processes. Activation of the immune system leads to the release of cytokines such as interleukin-1 and interleukin-6, which stimulate the hypothalamus to increase body temperature [2].

The diagnostic approach to FUO includes a detailed history and examination supported by tests. Age, exposure history, contact with wildlife, and medications should be noted. The examination should include, in addition to the general appearance, the presence of sweating, rash, tonsillitis, sinusitis, and swollen lymph nodes. Other signs such as abdominal tenderness and hepatosplenomegaly should be noted. It is necessary to carefully examine the muscles and bones for connective tissue diseases [3].

A complete blood count, smear test, and acute phase reagent levels should be part of the initial investigations. Radiologic imaging is a useful aid in the diagnosis of FUO. Antimicrobial trials should not be performed as they may obscure the diagnosis of the disease in FUO [4].

The purpose of this study is to analyze a clinical case of fever of unknown origin (FUO) in a child, to determine the etiology, pathogenesis and to develop diagnostic and therapeutic approaches for the effective detection and treatment of this condition.

Materials and methods. The study considers the clinical case of a 7-year-old girl. She has no chronic diseases, was born at term from the second pregnancy, second delivery. Birth weight 3500 g, body length 55 cm. She was vaccinated according to the vaccination schedule.

The patient had a fever lasting more than 3 weeks. The body temperature exceeded 38.3 °C. Preliminary examinations did not reveal a clear etiology. The girl complained of generalized weakness, abdominal pain and recurrent headaches. There was no history of contact with wild animals or travel to endemic areas.

- Medical history: No contact with wild animals, no travel to endemic areas.

- Physical examination: Presence of sweating, rash, swollen lymph nodes, abdominal tenderness and hepatosplenomegaly.

- Laboratory tests: A complete blood count showed an elevated level of leukocytes, rods and neutrophils, and C-reactive protein. The blood smear test did not reveal pathogenic microorganisms.

- Immunological tests: Elevated levels of antinuclear antibodies (ANA) and rheumatoid factor (RF).

- Radiological imaging: Ultrasound revealed enlargement of the liver and spleen.

Diagnostic interventions.

-Discontinuation of medications: In children with FUO, non-essential medications should be stopped. The disappearance of fever within two drug half-lives (usually three to four days) confirms the diagnosis of drug-induced fever.

Therapeutic trials:

- Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs): A therapeutic trial of NSAIDs is reasonable if juvenile idiopathic arthritis (JIA) is suspected. Resolution of fever confirms the diagnosis.

- Empirical antimicrobials: Antimicrobial therapy is generally avoided as a diagnostic measure in children with FUO, except for those with potentially life-threatening infections (e.g., malaria, typhoid, disseminated tuberculosis).

- Empirical glucocorticoids: Glucocorticoid testing should not be administered to children with FUO unless the child is extremely ill and infection and malignancy have been conclusively ruled out.

The child was in the department from 07/24/24 to 08/13/24 (21 days). The general condition of the child is satisfactory, not feverish. Consciousness is clear, the

girl is active. Appetite and sleep are preserved. She drinks fluids willingly. Hemodynamics and microcirculation are stable. The skin is pale pink, clean. Skin turgor and elasticity are satisfactory. Visible mucous membranes are clear, pale pink. Auscultatory breathing is vesicular, without wheezing. Heart sounds are clear, rhythmic. The abdomen is soft, not painful. Stool and diuresis are normal. Recommendations are given. Dynamic follow-up by a family doctor.

Diagnosis: D89.9. Disorder involving immune mechanism, unspecified

G93.2. Benign intracranial hypertension

Treatment: included the use of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) to reduce inflammation and fever. Immunomodulatory drugs were also prescribed to regulate the immune response. The patient received supportive care, including hydration and vitamins.

Further evaluation. Children with persistent FUO should be evaluated serially. For patients who can be evaluated on an outpatient basis, it is recommended to keep a fever diary and return to evaluate new complaints or changes in clinical status. The fever diary should include the date and time of fever onset, fever height and duration, method of fever assessment, and associated symptoms. Children who are hospitalized undergo a thorough physical examination and interval history daily, followed by a follow-up examination with new results [5-7].

If the FUO disappears in three to seven days, no further evaluation is performed. If the FUO persists and the child appears well, it is advisable to perform serial evaluations and obtain additional diagnostic tests only if new (or newly identified) symptoms or signs are present.

For children with persistent fever and no diagnosis after the initial evaluation, the following tests may be warranted (if not previously performed) [8-10]:

- Serum concentrations of immunoglobulins (Ig G, IgA, and IgM: To detect humoral immunodeficiency.

- Immunological analysis for combined antigen/antibody to HIV: To exclude HIV infection.

- Visualization of the gastrointestinal tract: To detect an occult abscess, tumor, or lymphadenopathy in patients with gastrointestinal complaints. Abdominal ultrasound is usually the first step, but CT or MRI may be necessary for patients with suspected malignancy or for urgent examination.

- Positron emission tomography (PET): FDG-PET can be useful for detecting tumors, infections, and inflammation, although studies in children are limited.

Other imaging methods are usually not helpful if there are no localization results. These include imaging of the central nervous system, labeled white blood cell scans, bone radiographs, technetium bone scans, and liver and spleen scans. Whole-body MRI may be useful for assessing the extent of multisystem disease in children with cancer and inflammatory diseases, but its usefulness in the routine evaluation of children with persistent FUO has not been established.

Conclusions. This clinical case emphasizes the importance of a detailed history, physical examination, and the use of modern diagnostic methods to identify

the etiology of FUO in children. Disorders involving the immune mechanism can be difficult to diagnose, but timely detection and treatment can improve prognosis.

Fever of unknown origin (FUO) in children is often a benign and/or self-limiting process. However, it is important to differentiate early benign causes from those that may be a manifestation of a serious condition or pose a life-threatening risk.

Initial evaluation of FUO requires confirmation of fever in a healthcare setting and a thorough reassessment of history and physical examination. Most cases of FUO are due to infectious causes, but a small percentage are due to other causes, including rheumatic or neoplastic diseases. In a high percentage of cases, the etiologic diagnosis is not established, which is a marker of spontaneous resolution.

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